

Deliverable D9.1 Report on mobilised sequence and variation data - relates to tasks 9.1-9.2

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WP leader(s):	Aitana Neves (SIB) & Nils P Willassen (UiT)		
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Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable:	EMBL-EBI		
Authors:	Guy Cochrane (EMBL-EBI), Zahra Waheed (EMBL-EBI), Nadim Rahman (EMBL-EBI)		
Contributors:	Marianna Ventouratou and members of ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP8 and WP9		
Acknowledgments (not grant participants):			
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Log of changes

DATE	Mv m	Who	Description
15/05/2023	0v1	Guy Cochrane (EMBL-EBI)	Initial version
01/06/2023	0v2	Aitana Neves (SIB)	Sent to PMO after incorporating internal WP feedback
19/06/2023	0v3	Juan Arenas (ELIXIR Hub)	Circulated to the MB for final review before submission
26/06/2023	0v4	Aitana Neves (SIB)	MB comments addressed
05/07/2023	1v0	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version to be uploaded into EC Portal

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1. Executive Summary

Mobilisation of SARS-CoV-2 data is a key output of the European COVID-19 Data Platform - which makes genomic and other biological data types, analysis and visualisation tools relating to SARS-CoV-2 freely available for the global scientific community. Sharing viral genome and variation data from around the world helps enable tracking of pathogen evolution, transmission and outbreak investigation, and ultimately contributes to the development of therapeutics. However, it is data mobilisation at scale which truly helps effective genomic surveillance take place. National sequencing centres are often prime candidates for this, as they can generate high volumes of genomic data over a long time period.

The scope of this deliverable was to maximise the mobilisation of SARS-CoV-2 sequence and variation data from national sequencing efforts as well as individual centres/labs into the European COVID-19 Data Platform. To achieve this, several aspects of user support were strengthened (including outreach to public health authorities) in addition to continuing the systematic analysis of raw SARS-CoV-2 reads in the INSDC as part of WP8.

Through the work described in this deliverable, EMBL-EBI helped support SARS-CoV-2 sequence data streams with national submitters (to encourage open sharing of data beyond SARS-CoV-2). Through WP8 designed analysis workflows, we also generated >3 million variant calls which not only present across the European COVID-19 Data Platform but also other integrated EBI resources for increased visibility and access.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	No
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	No
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	No
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	No
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and	No

researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	No
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	No
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	No
Key Result 3.4: Enable 'FAIR at source' practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	No
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No
Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	No
Objectives - WP9 - Mobilisation of SARS-CoV-2 variant surveillance data tracking services and tools	
O9.1 Coordinate nascent and established national data hubs focusing on brokering services to define and foster common best practices	No

09.2 Mobilise open SARS-CoV-2 genome data into the COVID-19 Data Platform (https://www.covid19dataportal.org) from individual data hubs.	Yes
09.3 Catalyse agreement on SARS-CoV-2 data standards for variants and lineages.	Yes
09.4 Drive development of SARS-CoV-2 variant analysis tools.	Yes

3. Introduction

The scope of this deliverable was to maximise mobilisation of SARS-CoV-2 sequence and variation data from individual centres/labs and national sequencing efforts into the European COVID-19 Data Platform, for FAIR and open access for the global scientific community. To do so, some of the work performed for this deliverable leverages the Platform infrastructure and analysis workflows developed as part of WP8.

As submission of the nucleotide sequence data is made to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) before presentation on the COVID-19 Data Portal, the availability of robust helpdesk support during all aspects of a submission (including data/metadata updates) and tools to facilitate rapid sharing of SARS-CoV-2 data are required for effective mobilisation at scale. This report highlights EMBL-EBI’s work in the former (as tool development has instead been described in WP8), as well as ENA’s interaction with the SARS-CoV-2 brokering community.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Mobilising sequence and variation data through strengthening user support

Submitting labs/centres vary in the scale and type of SARS-CoV-2 sequencing data they can submit, as well as their bioinformatics capacity and skillset, with all often being related. Thus the most appropriate submission interface for a submission to the European COVID-19 Data Platform will differ amongst users.

However, before an actual submission can take place, a number of decisions have to be made by a data submitter - including being aware of the submission routes/tools available and ensuring efficient integration with a user’s own system (also taking into account the frequency of their data sharing). Having robust helpdesk communication during these stages is key to optimise data mobilisation, as it improves the ease of data sharing, tailors support to each particular project context, and provides a point of contact for further queries that may arise even after successful data deposition.

Robust helpdesk support is also of particular importance for data brokers - groups who are likely responsible for mobilising high-volumes of sequence data on behalf of multiple national or international facilities.

Thus to strengthen user support, the following work has been accomplished by EMBL-EBI:

- EMBL-EBI continues to maintain the ENA's dedicated SARS-CoV-2 submission documentation¹ (in addition to the general documentation), incorporating feedback from users where appropriate
- EMBL-EBI continues to provide support through the ENA's dedicated SARS-CoV-2 helpdesk, virus-dataflow@ebi.ac.uk
- A SARS-CoV-2 submission tutorial² has been produced previously, and continues to be shared in SARS-CoV-2 data deposition training sessions

To better support and engage with large-scale submitters, EMBL EBI:

- continues to reach out and organise meetings with public health authorities and other groups involved in national sequencing efforts, in order to set up long-term data streams to the ENA. This includes providing additional user support via direct email to helpdesk staff
- helped to organise a Data Brokering Workshop in conjunction with WP8 and WP1 in September 2022. The aim of this was to better define brokering and the different contexts this can be performed in, across CONVERGE work packages. The workshop included a breakout session on developing a pathogen maturity model for national submitters, including data brokers

4.2 Mobilising sequence and variation data through systematic data analysis in WP8

SARS-CoV-2 sequence and variation data continue to be mobilised through the ongoing systematic analysis work performed in WP8, by EMBL-EBI in collaboration with partners of the external VEO project. This has been described in detail in deliverable 8.3³, though briefly, all SARS-CoV-2 raw read data submitted to the ENA continue to be processed through Oxford Nanopore or Illumina specific workflows to generate variant calls and consensus sequences. For public raw data, these are submitted back to the ENA as analysis objects (which are linked to the originally submitted raw data) for public access via the COVID-19 Data Portal⁴. Downstream, variant calls are also fed through EVA where they are accessioned and routed back to the COVID-19 Data Portal through the 'variants' section⁵ and Ensembl, where variant metadata such as predicted consequence is added.

This analysis service allows submitting centres, particularly in low resource settings where there may be a lack of bioinformatics expertise, compute/financial resources and time constraints for analysis, to freely share this data. This uniformity of the analysis helps standardise across different assembly programs/methods used when individual analysis is performed prior to genome submission, enabling

¹ https://ena-browser-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/help_and_guides/sars-cov-2-submissions.html

² https://ena-covid19-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submission_workshop/getting_started.html

³ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1-S7WZFTmsBJtRWBnKuRx1kcSmUbhexOusbAMXg-PCM/edit#heading=h.qxkf5yuhfiye>

⁴ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/search/sequences?crossReferencesOption=all&overrideDefaultDomain=true&db=sra-analysis-covid19&size=15>

⁵ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/search/sequences?crossReferencesOption=all&overrideDefaultDomain=true&db=eva-a-variants-covid19&size=15>

better downstream comparison between variant call and consensus sequence output across SARS-CoV-2 data in the INSDC, e.g. when users retrieve data in bulk.

4.2.1 Sequence and variation data visualisation

To improve variant monitoring and outbreak surveillance, variant call files from the systematic analysis continue to be fed into the CoVEO Variant Explorer, presenting in the COVID-19 Data Portal. Variants are sent to a custom database before presenting in CoVEO, and variant data summaries are provided in reports produced for the VEO project.

The COVID-19 Phylogeny, continues to present submitted SARS-CoV-2 genomes via the Evergreen and PhyloDash pipeline and application, developed by VEO partners, and integrated on EMBL-EBI infrastructure. The visualisation does have limitations stemming from the vast amount of data points on the phylogeny tree, resulting in a slow user experience. Upon review, there are lessons learned that have been discussed within the VEO project that would support better navigability and overall user experience.

5. Results

To date, 6,185,076 raw reads and 6,584,858 nucleotide sequences (including both assembled and consensus sequences) have been submitted to the European COVID-19 Data Portal (see Figure 1 below), from over 100 countries.

Figure 1. Graph showing growth in number of nucleotide sequences and raw reads submissions to the ENA since Jan 2020. Figure taken from the COVID-19 Data Portal statistics page⁶.

⁶ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/statistics>

5.1 Mobilising sequence and variation data through strengthening user support

Results from general user support:

- Since the end of 2022 the ENA SARS-CoV-2 helpdesk has seen a slight decrease in tickets; the average frequency of tickets in this queue in 2023 is 1 per week, while in early/mid 2022 this was 3 per week. However the nature of the queries (i.e submission guidance, error troubleshooting etc.) have largely remained the same. The reduction is likely due to the decrease in overall COVID sequencing and focus on other pathogen data instead. Indeed the dedicated ENA pathogen queue receives a higher volume of tickets more generally, with an average of 8-10 tickets weekly since the end of 2022.

As a result of improved support and engagement with large-scale submitters:

- In general, through outreach efforts over the course of the pandemic, over 20 national-level submitters shared their regional SARS-CoV-2 sequencing data with the ENA
- Some of these national-level submitters are brokers, who are not the main owners of the data and tend to set up a longer-term data stream to and with the ENA. A significant proportion of the SARS-CoV-2 data submissions mentioned above are from such data brokers -for example, after COG-UK, the Robert Koch Institute (RKI) in Germany and the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics (SIB) submitted the highest volume of assembled/consensus sequences (7.6% and 3% respectively).
- A notable outcome of the 2022 Data Brokering Workshop is the set up of a WP9 maturity model taskforce, focussing on the development of this for national pathogen data centres/hubs

5.2 Mobilising sequence and variation data through systematic data analysis in WP8

Of the Oxford Nanopore and Illumina based reads that have been submitted, 68% have been systematically analysed by the ENA, and as of March 2023, >3million processed datasets have been made available via CoVEO for browsing.

While implementing this has not been without its challenges (described in a manuscript currently being written for the VEO project), mobilising variation data from the majority of raw SARS-CoV-2 reads held within the INSDC has helped provide a comprehensive overview of circulating SARS-CoV-2 variants to the European Commission during the pandemic. To our knowledge this type of analysis has not been implemented before by another international genomic data repository.

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, EMBL-EBI has worked to maximise mobilisation of SARS-CoV-2 sequence and variation data by:

1. Continuing to support users to submit SARS-CoV-2 data to the COVID-19 Data Portal through email communication, and producing and maintaining training materials and documentation
2. Specifically for national-level submitters, providing additional support to set up tailored data streams to the ENA. This also builds rapport and further facilitates other types of data submissions to the ENA from the same groups
3. Continuing the work in WP8 to systematically analyse all SARS-CoV-2 raw read data submitted to the ENA/INSDC; generating variant calls and other analysis products that are fed back into the COVID-19 Portal. Here they present via a dedicated 'Systematic Analysis' tab, but also through the 'variants' section under the 'Viral sequences' tab, where they can be accessed through a number of search and download tools to suit the different needs of users. Finally, variants and submitted SARS-CoV-2 genomes are visualised through the CoVEO Variant Explorer and COVID-19 Phylogeny to provide insights for improved genomic surveillance
4. Sharing SARS-CoV-2 variant data across multiple EBI archives for public presentation. As variant calls are shared with the ENA, EVA and Ensembl in addition to the COVID-19 Data Portal, (and further annotated at EVA and Ensembl) this maximises visibility and reach of this data for users. Variant data also presents on Ensembl's own COVID-19 browser.

7. Impact

Not applicable

8. Next Steps

SARS-CoV-2 data submission support continues through all the methods described above. For outreach, we are increasingly focussing our efforts on national data submitters from Low and Middle Income Countries, such as those in Latin America. This ties in with other projects such as BY-COVID and ReCODID, by facilitating submissions of other infectious disease data through strengthening relationships with existing and new national submitters/brokers.

Another next step is to clear the backlog of SARS-CoV-2 raw reads to be analysed, which is ongoing through WP8. New SARS-CoV-2 submissions are picked up by the pipeline automatically.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable

